

19 Pomegranate ellagitannins (ETs) are transformed in the gut to ellagic acid (EA) and its
20 microbiota metabolites, urolithin A (Uro-A) and urolithin B (Uro-B). These compounds
21 exert anti-inflammatory effects *in vitro* and *in vivo*. The aim of this study was to
22 investigate the effects of Uro-A, Uro-B and EA on colon fibroblasts, cells that play a
23 key role in intestinal inflammation. CCD18-Co colon fibroblasts were exposed to a
24 mixture of Uro-A, Uro-B and EA, at concentrations comparable to those found in the
25 colon (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, 1 μ M EA), both in the presence or absence of IL-1 β
26 (1 ng/mL) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL), and the effects on fibroblasts migration and
27 monocytes adhesion were determined. The levels of several growth factors and adhesion
28 cytokines were also measured. The mixture of metabolites significantly inhibited colon
29 fibroblasts migration (~70%) and monocyte adhesion to fibroblasts (~50%). These
30 effects were concomitant with a significant downregulation of the levels of PGE₂, PAI-
31 1 and IL-8, as well as other key regulators of cell migration and adhesion. Of the three
32 metabolites tested, Uro-A, exhibited the most significant anti-inflammatory effects. Our
33 results show that a combination of the ET metabolites found in colon, urolithins and
34 EA, at concentrations achievable in the intestine after the consumption of pomegranate,
35 were able to moderately improve the inflammatory response of colon fibroblasts and
36 suggest that consumption of ETs-containing foods has potential beneficial effects on gut
37 inflammatory diseases.

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46 **KEYWORDS: Cell adhesion; cell migration; chemokines; growth factors;**

47 **microbiota metabolites**

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52 INTRODUCTION

53 The two major forms of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), Crohn's disease (CD) and
54 ulcerative colitis (UC), are chronic remittent or progressive inflammatory conditions
55 that may affect the entire gastrointestinal tract or the colonic mucosa, respectively, and
56 are associated with an increased risk for colon cancer (1). The incidence of IBD
57 continues to rise in both, the developed and developing world, indicating that
58 'Westernization' may be conditioning the expression of these disorders and that
59 environmental factors play a significant part in IBD (2). Of these, the diet is likely to
60 have an important as yet poorly defined role on the development and progress of the
61 intestinal inflammatory diseases with some dietary constituents contributing to the
62 disease whereas other may protect against it (3). In particular, the consumption of fruits,
63 vegetables, olive oil, grains and nuts has been inversely associated with CD (4). All
64 these plant derived foods are rich in polyphenols which have been extensively reported
65 to have anti-inflammatory properties (5). Since a large proportion of the dietary
66 polyphenols are not absorbed and these compounds and (or) its microbiota metabolites
67 accumulate in the intestine, the effects of these compounds against intestinal
68 inflammation have been investigated using animal models of colitis and in intestinal
69 cells treated with pro-inflammatory cytokines. These studies provide evidence that
70 polyphenols can effectively modulate intestinal inflammation (6).

71 More specifically, a pomegranate extract (PE) rich in ellagitannins (ETs) has been
72 shown to have anti-inflammatory properties in a rat model of induced colitis by
73 regulating the expression of genes involved in the inflammatory pathways, decreasing
74 inflammatory markers and preserving the colon epithelium architecture (7). ETs release
75 ellagic acid (EA) in the gut and both, ETs and EA, are poorly absorbed in the stomach

76 and small intestine and largely metabolized by unidentified bacteria in the intestinal
77 lumen to produce urolithins (dibenzopyranones), mostly urolithin-A (Uro-A) and
78 urolithin-B (Uro-B) (8) which can be found at relatively high concentrations in the
79 colon (μM levels) (7, 9). The intestinal anti-inflammatory properties of PE may be
80 attributed to the urolithins, in particular to Uro-A, which has also been reported to exert
81 anti-inflammatory activity *in vivo* (7) and in cell models of human colon myofibroblasts
82 (10) and of aortic endothelial cells (11).

83 Pro-inflammatory cytokines including tumour necrosis factor-alpha ($\text{TNF-}\alpha$) and
84 interleukin 1-beta ($\text{IL-1}\beta$) are essential in mediating the inflammatory response, causing
85 a disturbance in the intestinal barrier and increasing tissue penetration of luminal
86 antigens. Inhibition of the cytokine-induced increase in intestinal permeability has an
87 important protective effect against intestinal mucosal damage and development of
88 intestinal inflammation (12). Colonic subepithelial myofibroblasts which reside just
89 beneath the epithelial layer form part of the gut barrier. They are critically involved in
90 wound healing and intestine mucosa repair because of their ability to modulate
91 extracellular matrix components (ECM) (13). They also play an active role in the
92 immune response of the intestine. Upon activation, these cells produce soluble
93 cytokines, chemokines, adhesion proteins and growth factors and initiate the
94 recruitment of immune cells to the site of tissue injury and inflammation (14).

95 With a view to further elucidating some of the putative mechanisms by which dietary
96 ETs may contribute to protect against intestinal inflammation, in the present study, we
97 investigated some of the cellular and molecular responses associated with the exposure
98 of cytokine-activated human colon fibroblasts (CCD-18Co) to a mixture of Uro-A, Uro-
99 B and EA at concentrations representative of those that may be found *in vivo* in the
100 colon after the dietary intake of ET-containing foods. For comparative purposes, we

101 also examined the effects of the same levels of each of the individual compounds. We
102 specifically explored the effects of these ET metabolites on: i) colon fibroblasts
103 migration, ii) THP-1 monocyte adhesion to colon fibroblasts and iii) molecular markers
104 involved in migration (growth factors) and adhesion (adhesion proteins).

105

106 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

107

108 **Materials.** Urolithin-A (Uro-A, 3,8-dihydroxy-6H-dibenzo(b,d)pyran-6-one) and
109 Urolithin B (Uro-B, 3-hydroxy-6H-dibenzo(b,d)pyran-6-one) were chemically
110 synthesised by Kylolab S.A. (Murcia, Spain). Ellagic acid (EA), calcein-AM, human
111 recombinant TNF- α and 3-(4,5-Dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-tetrazolium
112 bromide (MTT) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, USA). Phosphate
113 Buffered Saline (PBS) was from Fisher Scientific (USA). Interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) was
114 obtained from Calbiochem (Darmstadt, Germany). DMSO was from Panreac
115 (Barcelona, Spain). Ultrapure Millipore water was used for all solutions.

116

117 **Cell culture.** Human acute monocytic THP-1 cells were obtained from the European
118 Collection of Cells Cultured (ECACC) (Salisbury, UK) and maintained in RPMI 1640
119 culture media containing 10% v/v foetal bovine serum (FBS), 2 mM L-glutamine, 100
120 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin (Gibco, Invitrogen S.A., Barcelona,
121 Spain) at a final pH 7.2–7.4 and maintained at 37°C under a 5% CO₂ / 95% air
122 atmosphere at constant humidity. Cells were seeded at 3–5×10⁵ cells/mL on 75 cm²
123 flasks (Nunc, Roskilde, Denmark) and subcultured every other day (cells concentration
124 in the culture media was always below 8×10⁵ cells/mL). Cells passages between 15 and
125 30 were used for the experiments. The myofibroblasts-like cell line CCD-18Co, derived
126 from a human colonic mucosal biopsy, was obtained from the American Type Culture
127 Collection (ATCC; Ref: CRL-1459) (Rockville, MD, USA). Unless otherwise stated,
128 cells were routinely grown in Eagle's minimum essential medium (EMEM) containing
129 10% v/v FBS and supplemented with 2 mM L-glutamine, 0.1 mM nonessential amino
130 acids, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, 1.5 g/L sodium bicarbonate, 100 U mL⁻¹ penicillin, 100
131 µg mL⁻¹ streptomycin (Gibco, Invitrogen S.A., Barcelona, Spain) at a final pH 7.2–7.4
132 and maintained at 37°C under a 5% CO₂ / 95% air atmosphere at constant humidity. The
133 culture medium was changed every 2–3 days until cells reached ~90% confluence. The
134 cells were then subcultured using Trypsin-EDTA (0.25%–0.03%). Cell cultures
135 between 16 and 19 population doubling levels (PDLs) were used for all the
136 experiments.

137

138 **Prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂) analysis.** Colon fibroblasts were seeded in 96-well plates
139 at an initial density of 1.2×10³ cells/well. At confluence, the culture medium was
140 removed and the cells washed twice with PBS before addition of fresh medium (0.1%
141 FBS) for 24 h. Next, the cells were treated with freshly prepared IL-1β (1 ng/mL) or

142 TNF- α (50 ng/mL) (dissolved in fresh culture medium, 0.1% FBS) alone or in
143 combination with each of the tested metabolites dissolved in DMSO and filtered
144 through 0.22 μ m prior adding to the cells): i) Uro-A (40 μ M), ii) Uro-B (5 μ M), iii) EA
145 (1 μ M) and iv) a mixture of these molecules (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M
146 EA; MIX) for 18 h (time point at which maximum production of PGE₂ is observed)
147 (10). Control cells were treated in parallel with the equivalent amount of DMSO (0.5 %
148 v/v). The culture medium was then removed and frozen at -80°C until analysis. PGE₂
149 levels were measured using an immunoenzymatic method (Cayman Chemicals, San
150 Diego, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions.

151

152 **Migration assay.** Colon fibroblasts migration was examined using the procedure
153 described by Giménez-Bastida *et al.* (11) with some modifications. CCD18-Co colon
154 fibroblasts were seeded in 6-wells plates at an initial density of 6.0×10^3 cells/cm² and
155 grown to ~90% confluence in fresh medium containing 10% FBS. Confluent
156 monolayers were then changed into fresh medium containing 0.1% FBS for 24 h and a
157 group of cells destroyed or displaced by scratching a line horizontally through the
158 monolayer with a sterile pipet tip. Media, dislodged cells and debris were aspirated and
159 cells washed twice with PBS before the culture medium was replaced by fresh medium
160 (0.1% FBS). Next, the cells were treated with each of the inflammatory cytokines IL-
161 1 β (1 ng/mL) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL) (dissolved in fresh culture medium, 0.1% FBS)
162 alone or in combination with each of the tested metabolites dissolved in DMSO and
163 filtered through 0.22 μ m prior adding to the cells): i) Uro-A (40 μ M), ii) Uro-B (5 μ M),
164 iii) EA (1 μ M) and iv) a mixture of these molecules (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1
165 μ M EA; MIX) for 48 h. Control cells were treated in parallel with the equivalent
166 amount of DMSO (0.5% v/v) . The open gap was inspected over time as the cells

167 moved in and filled the damaged area using a phase contrast inverted microscope.
168 Randomly selected views along the scraped line were photographed on each well using
169 a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera attached to the microscope. Three or four
170 selected views were photographed along the scraped area on each well immediately
171 after the treatment (time 0) and following 48 h of exposure. The average distance
172 between the two sides of the gap was determined by measuring the distance (μm)
173 between two points (n=10 measurements) along each photographed area. Final migrated
174 distance was calculated as the difference between the gap distance at time 0 and after 48
175 h of incubation. Data are representative of 3 experiments (n=2 wells per treatment).
176

177 **Cell viability assay.** Cell viability was estimated using the MTT assay. This assay
178 determines total mitochondrial activity which is related to the number of viable cells
179 and it is used to determine *in vitro* cytotoxic effects (15). The fibroblasts were cultured
180 in 24-wells plates at an initial density of 6.0×10^3 cells/cm² and were grown to ~90%
181 confluence in fresh medium containing 10% FBS. Cells were then treated as described
182 for the migration assay. Following 48 h of incubation, the culture medium was removed
183 and the cells washed twice with sterile PBS. Then, 1 mL of MTT solution (1.0 mg/mL
184 in FBS deprived-medium) was added to the cells and incubated for a further 4 h. The
185 formazan crystals formed in the viable cells were solubilised with 625 μ L of DMSO and
186 the optical density was measured at a test wavelength of 570 nm and a reference
187 wavelength of 690 nm using a microplate reader (Fluostar Galaxy, BMG Lab.
188 Technologies v5.0). Data are presented as the mean values \pm SD from 3 independent
189 experiments (n=2 wells per experiment).

191 **Cell adhesion assay.** Monocytes adhesion to colon fibroblasts was evaluated using
192 the human leukaemia monocytic THP-1 cells as previously described (11). Cultured
193 monocytes were resuspended in PBS (1×10^6 cells/mL) and labeled with 5 μ L/mL of
194 calcein-AM (5 μ M final concentration) for 30 min at 37° C. The cells were then
195 centrifuged at 150 \times g for 5 min and washed twice with PBS before addition to the
196 fibroblasts. Colon fibroblasts were cultured in 96-wells plates at a concentration of
197 1.2×10^4 cells/well in fresh medium containing 10% FBS. Confluent cells were co-
198 incubated with freshly prepared IL-1 β (1 ng/mL) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL) (dissolved in
199 fresh culture medium) alone or in combination with each of the tested metabolites
200 dissolved in DMSO and filtered through 0.22 μ m prior adding to the cells): i) Uro-A

201 (40 μ M), ii) Uro-B (5 μ M), iii) EA (1 μ M) and iv) a mixture of these molecules (40 μ M
202 Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA; MIX) for 12 h. Control cells were treated in parallel
203 with the equivalent amount of DMSO (0.5 % v/v). After treatment, the fibroblasts were
204 washed twice with PBS and co-incubated with the calcein-labeled monocytes (2×10^5
205 cells per well) in the dark for 1 h at 37° C. Non-adhering cells were removed and the
206 remaining cells washed twice with PBS before fluorescence was measured with a
207 fluorescence-detecting microplate reader (Fluostar Galaxy, BMG Lab. Technologies
208 v5.0) using excitation at 492 nm and emission at 520 nm. Experiments were carried out
209 in triplicate (n=6 wells per treatment).

210

211 **Measurement of growth factors, adhesion molecules and cytokines by ELISA.**

212 Cell lysates were used to analyse specific molecules using the following commercially
213 available human ELISA kits: platelet-derived growth factor beta polypeptide (PDGF-
214 BB; Preprotech, Rocky Hill, NJ, USA), β -type platelet-derived growth factor receptor
215 (PDGF-R- β ; Sino Biological, Schilde, Belgium), s-ICAM-1 (Bender MedSystems,
216 Vienna, Austria) and VCAM-1 (Gen-Probe, San Diego, USA). The minimum detection
217 levels were 62 pg/mL and 62.5 pg/mL for PDGF-BB and PDGF-R- β , respectively, and
218 6.25 ng/mL and 0.6 ng/mL for s-ICAM-1 and VCAM-1, respectively. The protein
219 content of the cell lysates was measured by the *DC* colorimetric assay at 750 nm
220 (BioRad, Barcelona, Spain) using a microplate reader (Infinite M200, Tecan, Grodig,
221 Austria) and based on a BSA standard curve. Culture medium was used for the analysis
222 of interleukin-8 (IL-8), interleukin-6 (IL-6), plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1)
223 and monocyte chemotactic protein-1 (MCP-1 or CCL2) using commercially available
224 ELISA kits from Peprotech (Rocky Hill, NJ, USA). The minimum detection level was 8
225 pg/mL for IL-8 and MCP-1, 32 pg/mL for IL-6 and 23 pg/mL for PAI-1. Analysis of the

226 intensity related to the concentration was measured using a microplate reader (Infinite
227 M200, Tecan, Grodig, Austria). Data are presented as the mean value from three to six
228 independent experiments \pm SD.

229

230 **Human antibody arrays.** Changes in the expression levels of proteins involved in
231 cell migration and cell adhesion were investigated using: i) human antibody membrane
232 arrays RayBio® Human Growth Factor Array which contains 41 growth factors and, ii)
233 custom designed human antibody arrays containing 20 markers of adhesion
234 (RayBiotech, Inc., Norcross, GA, USA) following the manufacturer's
235 recommendations. The configuration of the antibody arrays is given in the
236 Supplementary Figures 1 and 2. CCD18-Co colon-fibroblasts were cultured in 10-cm
237 plates at an initial density of 6.0×10^3 cells/cm². Confluent cells were treated with the
238 pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β (1 ng/mL) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL) alone or in
239 combination with Uro-A (40 μ M) or the mixture of metabolites (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M
240 Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA; MIX) in 0.1% FBS (v/v) culture media for 48 h (growth factors)
241 or in 10% FBS (v/v) culture media for 12 h (adhesion proteins). After treatment, the
242 culture medium was removed and frozen at -80°C until analysis. The cells were washed
243 twice with PBS and lysed with 0.5 mL of ice-cold lysis RIPA buffer containing a
244 cocktail of proteases inhibitors (Roche, Manheim, Germany). Cell lysates were
245 centrifuged at $23200 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and frozen at -80°C until analysis. The protein
246 content of the cell lysates was measured by the *DC* colorimetric assay at 750 nm
247 (BioRad, Barcelona, Spain) using a microplate reader (Infinite M200, Tecan, Grodig,
248 Austria) and based on a BSA standard curve. Total equivalent amounts of protein (300
249 μ g) were incubated with the arrays for 2 h at room temperature. Detection was
250 performed with biotin-conjugated antibodies raised against the particular molecules and

251 horseradish peroxidase-conjugated streptavidin. Arrays were visualized using a CCD
252 camera coupled to a Chemidoc 881XRS equipment (Biorad Laboratories, Barcelona,
253 Spain). Non-saturated spots were scanned and converted to densitometric units using
254 the software ScanAlyze (16). The proteins were represented in duplicate per array.
255 Negative controls and blank spots were used to determine the background. Raw data
256 (intensity value of each spot) were subtracted from the averaged background and
257 normalized according to positive control densities. Differences in protein expression
258 between experimental groups are expressed as fold-change. Proteins showing changes
259 in expression ≥ 1.3 -fold or < 1.3 -fold were considered as up-regulated or down-regulated
260 respectively (because modest changes in expression may have biological significance).
261 Triplicate (IL-1 β treated cells) or duplicate experiments (TNF- α treated cells) were
262 performed for each treatment. Data are presented as the mean value \pm SD.

263

264 **Statistical analyses.** Results are presented as mean values \pm SD (displayed as error
265 bars). Where indicated, data were statistically analyzed using PASW statistics 18.0
266 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL) and differences between experimental groups were made using
267 two-tailed unpaired Student's *t* test. Results with a *P* value < 0.001 , < 0.01 or < 0.05 were
268 considered significant. Results showing a trend with *P* values < 0.1 are also indicated.

269

270 **RESULTS**

271 **Effects of the urolithins and (or) EA on PGE₂ levels.** Our results showed that
272 exposure to IL-1 β (1 ng/mL, 18 h) caused a very significant induction (36.0 ± 1.6 -fold;
273 $P < 0.001$) in the production of PGE₂ by the colon fibroblasts which was completely
274 attenuated by co-treatment with the MIX metabolites (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, 1
275 μ M EA) ($P < 0.001$) or Uro-A (40 μ M) (Figure 1a). Uro-B (5 μ M) also reduced the levels
276 of PGE₂ in a significant manner (66.5% reduction, $P < 0.001$) while EA had no
277 effect on the synthesis of PGE₂ (Figure 1a). Treatment of the colon fibroblasts with
278 TNF- α , alone or in combination with the metabolites (Figure 1b), or exposure of the
279 cells to the metabolites in the absence of cytokine (Figure 1c) had no significant effects
280 on the levels of PGE₂.

281

282 **Effect of the urolithins and (or) EA on colon fibroblasts migration, cell viability**
283 **and related molecular markers.** To investigate whether the mixture of metabolites or
284 the individual compounds exerted any anti-inflammatory phenotypic responses on the
285 human colon fibroblasts, we next examined the effects of these compounds on the
286 fibroblasts ability to migrate. The effect of the urolithins and (or) EA, alone or in
287 combination with the cytokines, on the migration of CCD18-Co cells is shown in Figure
288 2. Induction of migration with IL-1 β was moderate (24%, $P<0.1$) (Figure 2a) and both
289 the MIX metabolites and Uro-A as well as EA significantly inhibited IL-1 β -induced
290 migration by 69% ($P<0.001$), 57% ($P<0.01$) and 38% ($P<0.001$), respectively. Colon
291 fibroblast migration was also moderately but significantly induced after treatment with
292 TNF- α for 48 h (29% induction; $P<0.01$; Figure 2b) and inhibited by co-treatment with
293 the MIX (70%), Uro-A (54%) and EA (19%) ($P<0.001$). In the absence of the
294 inflammatory cytokines, colon fibroblasts migration was significantly inhibited by the
295 MIX metabolites (64%, $P<0.01$; Figure 2c). Uro-A exhibited a smaller and less
296 significant inhibitory effect (35%; $P<0.1$) whereas Uro-B or EA did not have a direct
297 effect on fibroblast migration.

298 In order to determine whether exposure of the colon fibroblasts to the urolithins and
299 (or) EA for 48 h were inducing gross changes in the cells which may indicate some kind
300 of toxicity of the treatments and (or) alteration of the cell proliferation rate, the effects
301 of the metabolites on total mitochondrial activity were assessed using the MTT assay
302 (Figure 3). Activation with IL-1 β alone or in combination with the metabolites did not
303 have a significant effect on the cells viability (Figure 3a). Exposure of the fibroblasts to
304 TNF- α had a small but significant detrimental effect on the cells mitochondrial activity
305 (35% inhibition, $P<0.001$; Figure 3b) which was slightly recovered following exposure
306 to the MIX metabolites or Uro-A. Neither the MIX nor the individual metabolites, in the

307 absence of cytokine, caused significant changes in the rates of MTT reduction at the
308 concentrations tested providing evidence that the cell responses to the urolithins or EA
309 were not likely to be due to gross toxic effects on the cells (Figure 3c).

310 We also investigated the changes in the levels of PAI-1 using an ELISA assay
311 (Figure 4) which was highly up-regulated after treatment with the cytokines (6.5 ± 0.7
312 and 4.5 ± 0.3 for IL-1 β and TNF- α , respectively; $P < 0.001$) and down-regulated
313 following exposure to the MIX or Uro-A for 48 h, more significantly in the IL-1 β -
314 treated cells (0.5 ± 0.2 , $P < 0.01$ and 0.6 ± 0.3 , respectively; $P < 0.05$). In addition, we
315 were not able to detect any significant effects on the levels of PDGF-BB or PDGF-R- β
316 in colon fibroblasts after IL-1 β or TNF- α stimulation for 48 h, either alone or in
317 combination with Uro-A or the MIX using the ELISA technique (results not shown).
318

319 **Search for further growth and migration factors modulated by the cytokines**
320 **and the ET metabolites using antibody arrays.** Since inhibition of fibroblast
321 migration was most significant following exposure to the MIX of metabolites and Uro-
322 A, we selected these treatments for the subsequent screening of further changes in
323 growth factors that may be associated to the responses of the CCD18-Co using human
324 antibody arrays. The complete profile of growth factors represented on the array (ranked
325 in order of spot intensity from highest to lowest value) and the differences detected for

326 each one between the experimental groups (fold-change) are included in Supplementary
327 Tables 1 and 2. Both cytokines, IL-1 β and TNF- α , caused a general upregulation of
328 many of the growth factors represented on the chip (80% and 60%, respectively) while
329 the MIX and Uro-A downregulated some of those. Fold-changes were also, in general,
330 very moderate with most changes ranging between 1.3 and 3.0. Table 1 summarizes the
331 comparative results between IL-1 β and TNF- α -treated cells for some of the major
332 growth factor families that participate in cell migration and wound healing. Whereas
333 treatment with IL-1 β was concomitant with the upregulation of all the main members of
334 these growth factors families, exposure to TNF- α did not modify the levels of the TGF β
335 family, some VEGF members or some of the macrophage colony stimulating factors. In
336 the IL-1 β stimulated cells, exposure to the MIX or Uro-A was associated to the
337 downregulation of most of the growth factors selected whereas in the TNF- α -treated
338 fibroblasts, results exhibited more variation with some growth factors resulting further
339 upregulated by exposure to the MIX (FGF6, TGF β members, some VEGF members and
340 M-CSF) or Uro-A (bFGF and IGFBP-3). It should be noted that, unlike the results
341 obtained with the ELISA assays, the antibody arrays indicated that stimulation of the
342 colon CCD-18Co fibroblasts with each of the cytokines was accompanied by an
343 induction of the levels of PDGF-BB or PDGF-R- β which were downregulated by the
344 metabolites.

345

346 **Effect of the urolithins and (or) EA on monocyte adhesion to colon fibroblasts**
347 **and related molecular markers.** We next investigated the effects of the ET
348 metabolites on THP-1 monocyte adhesion. Incubation of the CCD18-Co cells with IL-
349 1 β (1 ng/mL; Figure 5a) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL; Figure 5b) for 12 h significantly
350 increased the monocytes adhesiveness by 50% and 32%, respectively ($P < 0.001$). Of the

351 metabolites tested, Uro-A and EA significantly inhibited monocyte adhesion on IL-1 β
352 treated cells by 20% ($P<0.05$) whereas Uro-B and EA moderately but significantly
353 inhibited monocyte adhesion on TNF- α treated cells by 22% ($P<0.05$). The most
354 significant inhibition was observed following exposure of the cytokine-activated colon
355 cells to the MIX of metabolites (35% and 50% inhibition, respectively, $P<0.001$). None
356 of the compounds tested had any effect on monocyte adhesion in the absence of the
357 inflammatory cytokines (Figure 5c).

358 We also measured the concentration of selected chemokines and adhesion molecules
359 in control cells and cells exposed to Uro-A or the MIX metabolites (Figures 6 a-d) using
360 ELISA assays. The results show that stimulation of the CCD18-Co fibroblasts with the
361 pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β (1 ng/mL) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL) for 12 h
362 significantly ($P<0.001$) upregulated the expression of IL-8 (fold-change: 17.4 ± 3.5 and
363 12.0 ± 1.6 , respectively), CCL2 (2.4 ± 0.2 and 1.8 ± 0.1), ICAM-1 (11.9 ± 0.9 and $8.4 \pm$
364 0.6) and VCAM-1 (3.4 ± 1.1 and 3.8 ± 1.1). Co-treatment of the inflamed colon
365 fibroblasts with the ETs metabolites revealed that the levels of IL-8 released to the cell
366 culture media were only significantly downregulated by the MIX (0.6 ± 0.3) and by
367 Uro-A (0.7 ± 0.2) ($P<0.05$) in the TNF- α -treated cells (Figure 6a). Neither Uro-A or the
368 MIX metabolites showed any effect on the levels of CCL2 (Figure 6b). However, the
369 MIX metabolites were able to reduce the expression levels of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 in
370 the IL-1 β -treated cells (0.7 ± 0.2 , $P<0.05$) and (0.7 ± 0.1 , $P<0.1$), respectively (Figures
371 6c and 6d). The levels of these two adhesion proteins were shown to be unmodified
372 following treatment of cells with TNF- α and the metabolites (Figures 6c and 6d). IL-6
373 was also highly induced both by TNF- α and IL-1 β following 12 h and 48 h of
374 incubation to each of the cytokines but none of the tested metabolites had any effect on
375 the expression on this cytokine (results not shown).

376 **Search for further adhesion proteins modulated by the cytokines and the ET**
377 **metabolites using antibody arrays.** We were also able to search for additional
378 adhesion markers that may be modulated in the CCD-18Co cells following exposure to
379 TNF- α and to TNF- α + the MIX metabolites and that may be associated to the
380 regulation of monocyte adhesion to these colon fibroblasts. The complete profile of
381 adhesion proteins represented on the array (ranked in order of spot intensity from
382 highest to lowest value) and the differences (fold-change) detected for each one between
383 the experimental groups are included in Supplementary Table 3. A summary of those
384 adhesion markers that were upregulated by the cytokine and downregulated by the MIX
385 metabolites is presented in Table 2. In agreement with the ELISA assays, densitometric
386 analysis of the arrays showed that IL-8, CCL2, ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 were all highly
387 up-regulated in the CCD18-Co cells following treatment with TNF- α . Co-treatment
388 with the MIX metabolites showed a tendency to down-regulate the levels of IL-8
389 whereas the levels of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 were not affected as also shown by the
390 ELISA assays. However, and unlike the results of the ELISA assays, the arrays also
391 indicated a small (but significant) downregulation of the levels of CCL2 by the MIX in
392 the TNF- α -treated cells. Other adhesion proteins such as ALCAM, BCAM and CDH1
394 were also found to be upregulated by TNF- α and downregulated by the MIX.

395

396 **DISCUSSION**

397 The current treatment of intestinal chronic inflammation consists of long-term anti-
398 inflammatory therapy that does not exclude relapses, side effects and surgery. Many
399 dietary polyphenols exert anti-inflammatory effects in animal models and cultured cells
400 and have been proposed as an alternative natural approach to prevent or treat chronic

401 inflammatory diseases. The anti-inflammatory properties of polyphenols may be
402 especially relevant in the intestine where they can reach considerable concentrations
403 through the regular intake of polyphenol rich foods (6). Yet, to fully understand the
404 intestinal anti-inflammatory actions of dietary polyphenols it is crucial to: (i) identify
405 and quantify the actual metabolites found *in vivo* in the gut and (ii) unravel the
406 underlying molecular mechanisms triggered by these metabolites in the specific target
407 cells involved in the intestine inflammatory response. In the present work, we have
408 addressed these two important points by investigating some of the anti-inflammatory
409 effects and potential molecular mechanisms of the main colon microbiota metabolites
410 derived from the dietary polyphenols ETs against fibroblasts of the colon mucosa. We
411 found that a mixture of Uro-A, Uro-B and EA, at concentrations representative of those
412 that may be achieved in the gut through the diet, significantly inhibited two critical
413 processes of the intestine inflammatory response: fibroblasts migration and monocyte
414 adhesion. These effects were associated with a significant downregulation of the levels
415 of PGE₂, PAI-1 and IL-8, key regulators of cell migration and adhesion. Of the three
416 metabolites tested, Uro-A, exhibited the most significant anti-inflammatory effects.

417 In this study we investigated the response of the myofibroblast-like human cell line
418 (CCD-18Co) since these cells are noncancerous and are representative of colon
419 fibroblasts that lie underneath the gut epithelium. These cells constitute an important
420 and active component in the maintenance of the intestinal mucosa. Although colon
421 fibroblasts are less likely to be in direct contact with the luminal dietary compounds,
422 transient increase in the permeability of the tight junctions under inflammatory
423 conditions make possible the passage of many nutrients and small molecules through
424 the paracellular route (17). In addition, chronic inflammation may lead to disruption of
425 the epithelial barrier allowing for direct contact of luminal content with the cells

426 resident in the lamina propria. Therefore, it is conceivable that colon fibroblasts may
427 become exposed to significant quantities of colon dietary metabolites. Uro-A was the
428 most abundant ET-derived metabolite detected in the faeces of pigs and humans,
429 followed by Uro-B and trace quantities of EA (8, 18). In rats fed a high dose of
430 pomegranate, Uro-A (7–34 μM), Uro-B (2–65 μM) and EA (minor quantities) were
431 quantified in the colon (9). Based on these results as well as on the maximum solubility
432 of urolithins and EA in the cell culture medium (40 μM and 30 μM , respectively) (10)
433 we treated the colon fibroblasts with 40 μM Uro-A, 5 μM Uro-B and 1 μM EA.

434 Myofibroblasts in the colon mucosa play an important modulatory role in the
435 intestine inflammatory response partially by releasing PGE_2 (19). We had previously
436 established the association between the consumption of PE or Uro-A with the
437 downregulation of the levels of PGE_2 in the rat colon mucosa under inflammatory
438 conditions (7). Using human colon CCD-18Co fibroblasts, we had also evidenced that
439 Uro-A and Uro-B, at 1 and 10 μM concentrations, were able to counteract the induction
440 of PGE_2 by the pro-inflammatory cytokine $\text{IL-1}\beta$ (10) but a synergistic effect of the ET
441 metabolites was not investigated. In the present work, we have confirmed that a mixture
442 of the two urolithins and EA, at concentrations representative of those that may be
443 found in the gut through the consumption of ET rich products, is able to fully reverse
444 the $\text{IL-1}\beta$ -induction of PGE_2 and that these effects are mainly due to Uro-A. However,
445 $\text{TNF-}\alpha$, another key inflammatory cytokine, or the metabolites themselves did not show
446 any effect on the levels of PGE_2 . Although $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ has been reported to upregulate the
447 levels of this prostaglandin in CCD-18Co cells, the degree of inducibility varies
448 considerably and it has been shown to be much more pronounced with $\text{IL-1}\beta$ than with
449 $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ (20). More in agreement with our results, in a recent study, it was shown that
450 exposure of the CCD-18Co cells to $\text{TNF-}\alpha$ (8.3 ng/mL, 4 h) did not have a significant

451 effect on the production and secretion of PGE₂ by these cells (21). The prostaglandin
452 PGE₂ has an important regulatory role on several key fibroblasts functions including
453 fibroblasts migration and has been reported to be able to stimulate or inhibit fibroblasts
454 migration (19, 22). An important mechanism involved in wound healing and tissue
455 formation in the intestine is the migration of colonic lamina propria fibroblasts from
456 neighboring tissue to inflammation site and damaged mucosa. This response is
457 considered to be mediated by a complex chemotactic gradient with some molecules
458 inducing or enhancing migration whereas other molecules reduce the ability of these
459 cells to migrate. In addition to PGE₂, the pro-inflammatory cytokines, TNF- α and IL-1 β ,
460 have also important regulatory effects on cell migration (12–14). To further explore the
461 response of the colon fibroblasts to exposure to the ETs metabolites, we investigated the
462 effects of these compounds, alone or in the presence of the pro-inflammatory cytokines,
463 on the ability of these cells to migrate. Under the conditions of our assay, both TNF- α
464 and IL-1 β were able to increase colon fibroblasts migration in agreement with a pro-
465 fibrotic effect important to recruit activated fibroblasts into wounding sites as part of the
466 inflammatory and healing process. This effect resulted inhibited by co-treatment with
467 the ET metabolites suggesting an apparent interference with the normal wound healing
468 and tissue restitution. In contrast to our finding, TNF- α has also been reported to reduce
469 the migration of cultured colon lamina propria fibroblasts (23). Differences on the
470 effects of the pro-inflammatory cytokines on cell migration, and in particular of TNF- α ,
471 can only be understood in view of the complexity of its actions. TNF- α may exert both
472 immunomodulatory and disease-suppressive activities but also to initiate and sustain
473 chronic inflammatory conditions (24). The effects depend on many factors including
474 cell microenvironment and tissue source or the dose and time of exposure (25). When
475 the homeostatic mechanisms controlling wound healing become disordered in chronic

476 intestinal inflammatory diseases, reduction of the colon fibroblasts migration by the ETs
477 metabolites might protect against excessive fibrosis. The inhibitory effects of the ET
478 metabolites appear to be independent of the levels of PGE₂ since inhibition was
479 observed in cells treated IL-1 β (associated to the induction of PGE₂) as well as in cells
480 treated with TNF- α or in resting cells where the levels of PGE₂ were unaffected.

481 Another key molecule associated with inflammatory reactions in the intestine
482 mucosa and with a crucial regulatory role on fibroblasts migration is PAI-1 (17).
483 Although the net effect of PAI-1 on cell motility depends on many factors (i.e. ECM
484 composition, concentration of PAI-1, expression of cell receptors, etc), in general, the
485 expression of PAI-1 is highly induced in the migratory phenotype whereas migration is
486 reduced in low PAI-1 levels (26). In agreement with this, our results indicate that
487 induction of colon fibroblast migration by TNF- α and IL-1 β is associated to a
488 significant induction of PAI-1 and that inhibition of the process by the MIX metabolites
489 or Uro-A is concomitant with the downregulation of PAI-1. Cell migration and wound
490 healing is, however, a very complex process which involves the interaction and
491 regulation of multiple cell and factors (27). We further investigated the effects of the
492 ETs metabolites on several growth factor families known to be involved in cell growth
493 and migration using antibody arrays. Under proinflammatory conditions such as those
494 occurring during acute wounds, the cytokines IL-1 β and TNF- α are upregulated and
495 activate other cells such as fibroblasts to produce high levels of various growth factors
496 (27, 28). Also, transcriptional analyses of migrating human keratinocytes have
497 associated the up-regulation of PAI-1 with the up-regulation of various growth factors,
498 i.e. VEGF, PDGF- β and TGF- β 1 (29). In agreement with this, our results show that
499 exposure of the colon fibroblasts to the inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β or TNF- α was
500 concomitant with the up-regulation of PAI-1 levels and with a general up-regulation of

501 some key growth factors, such as members of the EGF, FGF, PDGF and IGF families.
502 Of particular interest, the PDGF family and its receptors, and more specifically, PDGF-
503 BB and PDGF-R β -induced signaling are likely important in the development of
504 intestinal fibrosis (30). Our results using the antibody arrays also show a general
505 downregulation of these PDGFs by the MIX metabolites or Uro-A suggesting a
506 potential preventive mechanism of these molecules against fibrotic disorders. Although
507 we were not able to reproduce the changes on the levels of PDGF-BB or PDGF-R- β
508 using some ELISA assays, our array results are in good agreement with those
509 previously published by us (11), in which we also showed that PDGFBB, PDGFAB,
510 PDGFAA and PDGF-R- β were all upregulated in human aortic endothelial cells by the
511 inflammatory cytokine TNF- α and downregulated after exposure to Uro-A. The
512 regulation of the levels of the placental growth factor (PIGF) should also be noted since,
513 it has been reported that high levels of PIGF induce the expression of PAI-1 (31) and
514 that PIGF absence strongly inhibits mucosal intestinal angiogenesis in acute colitis (32).
515 Our results show that both the MIX metabolites and Uro-A downregulated the levels of
516 PIGF in the cytokine-induced colon fibroblasts. A similar response was also seen in
517 human aortic endothelial cells (11).

518 During inflammation, chemokines such as IL-8 and CCL-2 as well as adhesion
519 molecules (ICAM-1) are induced in colonic subepithelial myofibroblasts in response to
520 IL-1 β and TNF- α (33, 34). These molecules are involved in the processes of infiltration
521 and adhesion of neutrophils and monocytes to the site of inflammation and exhibit high
522 levels of expression in inflammatory colon diseases (35). In order to further characterize
523 the anti-inflammatory mechanisms of the ETs metabolites, we also examined the effects
524 of these metabolites on the adhesion of monocytes to colon fibroblasts as well as on the
525 production of relevant chemokines and adhesion proteins. Our results show that

526 monocyte adhesion was moderately induced by the pro-inflammatory cytokines and
527 attenuated, primarily, by the MIX metabolites. This reducing effect was, however,
528 related to apparently different mechanisms in the TNF- α - and the IL-1 β -treated cells.
529 Like this, reduction of monocyte adhesion in the TNF- α -induced cells by the MIX was
530 concomitant with the downregulation of IL-8 secretion. This downregulation was also
531 observed following treatment with Uro-A, in agreement with previous results where
532 Uro-A was shown to diminish the levels of IL-8 in TNF- α -stimulated human endothelial
533 aortic cells (11). In the IL-1 β -treated cells, the MIX did not affect the levels of IL-8 but
534 caused a small decrease in the adhesion molecules ICAM-1 and VCAM-1. A similar
535 response in which the reduction of ICAM-1 expression was observed in cells exposed to
536 IL-1 β but not in those treated with TNF- α has been reported as specific effects of anti-
537 inflammatory corticosteroids on Crohn's fibroblasts (34). With regards to CCL2
538 regulation, results were less clear since we were only able to detect a small
539 downregulation of this monocyte chemoattractant protein following treatment with the
540 MIX metabolites in the TNF- α -induced fibroblasts using antibody arrays.

541 Our results show some agreement but also some differences between the results
542 obtained by RayBio antibody arrays and those obtained with the ELISA assays.
543 Although the antibody array technology has improved substantially and has been
544 efficiently validated by ELISA assays (36, 37), it is still a rather expensive technique
545 which limits the number of samples that can be done. This has a substantial effect on the
546 reproducibility of the data. In general, for proteins with higher levels of expression and
547 (or) exhibiting greater changes such as those induced by the cytokines (IL-1 β or TNF-
548 α), results were more easily replicated and confirmed by the ELISA assays. For modest
549 changes such as those induced by dietary compounds at low concentrations, results are
550 less reproducible. We cannot discard that some of the discordances between the arrays

551 and the ELISA assays may also be caused by differences between the antibodies used in
552 each technique.

553 General remarks: there is an increasing number of *in vitro* studies in the Literature
554 looking at the bioactivity of polyphenols at conditions more representative of the *in vivo*
555 situation following the dietary intake of these compounds, i.e. testing low
556 concentrations of the appropriate mixed metabolites against suitable cell models. It does
557 appear that, in general, under these conditions the metabolites induce very modest
558 phenotypic responses associated also to a very modest modulation of multiple target
559 proteins (as it may be expected for dietary compounds). These effects are indeed more
560 complex to validate than those resulting from the use of pharmacological doses of a
561 particular drug or compound and will demand further efforts in order to provide
562 evidence of the role of polyphenol metabolites on human health effects. The work
563 presented here is step forward in this direction. Overall, our results support the
564 hypothesis that μM concentrations of polyphenol-derived metabolites that can be
565 achieved in the gut through the diet can exert immunomodulatory effects on cells of the
566 intestinal barrier and contribute to the prevention on intestinal inflammatory diseases.

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575 **ABBREVIATIONS: IBDs**, inflammatory bowel diseases; **CD**, Crohn's disease; UC,
576 ulcerative disease; **PE**, pomegranate extract; **EA**, ellagic acid; **ETs**, ellagitannins; **CCD-**
577 **18Co**, human colon fibroblasts; **PBS**, phosphate buffered saline; **IL-1 β** , interleukin one
578 beta; **TNF- α** , tumor necrosis factor alpha; **Uro-A**, urolithin A; **Uro-B**, urolithin B.

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600 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION AVAILABLE**

601 The configuration of the RayBio antibody arrays is given in the Supplementary Figures
602 1 and 2. The complete profile of growth factors and adhesion proteins represented on
603 the array (ranked in order of spot intensity from highest to lowest value) and the
604 differences detected for each one between the experimental groups (fold-change) are
605 included in Supplementary Tables 1 to 3. This material is available free of charge via
606 the Internet at <http://pbs.acs.org>.

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754 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

755 **Figure 1.** Levels of PGE₂ in the supernatants from CCD18-Co colon fibroblasts
756 exposed to: a) IL-1 β (1 ng/mL), b) TNF- α (50 ng/mL), alone or in combination with
757 Uro-A (40 μ M), Uro-B (5 μ M), EA (1 μ M) or a mixture of these molecules (40 μ M
758 Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA; MIX), and c) metabolites in the absence of
759 cytokine, for 18 h. Data are presented as the mean value from three independent
760 experiments \pm SD. Symbols indicate differences from the cytokine-treated samples, ***
761 $P < 0.001$.

761

762 **Figure 2.** Effects of Uro-A (40 μ M), Uro-B (5 μ M), EA (1 μ M) and a mixture of these
763 molecules (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA; MIX) on CCD18-Co colon
764 fibroblasts migration: a) co-treatment with IL-1 β (1 ng/mL), b) co-treatment with TNF-
765 α (50 ng/mL), and c) in the absence of the inflammatory cytokines. Histograms show
766 the final migrated distance calculated as the difference between the gap distance at time
767 0 and after 48 h of exposure. Data are representative of three separate experiments
768 (mean value \pm SD). Symbols indicate differences from: a) and b) cytokine-treated
769 samples, c) control (CT) cells, # $P < 0.1$, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. d)

770 Representative photomicrographs showing migration of CCD18-Co fibroblasts in control
771 medium (CT) at times 0 h and 48 h, effect of the MIX on resting cells and effect
772 of IL-1 β or TNF- α alone and in combination with the MIX.

773

774 **Figure 3.** Effects of Uro-A (40 μ M), Uro-B (5 μ M), EA (1 μ M) and a mixture of these
775 molecules (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA; MIX) on CCD18-Co colon
776 fibroblasts viability using the MTT assay after 48 h of exposure: a) co-treatment with

777 IL-1 β (1 ng/mL), b) co-treatment with TNF- α (50 ng/mL), and c) in the absence of the
778 inflammatory cytokines. The results from three separate experiments are expressed as
779 mean percentage of untreated control \pm SD. Symbols indicate differences from TNF- α -
780 treated samples, # $P < 0.1$, * $P < 0.05$, *** $P < 0.001$.
781

782 **Figure 4.** Levels of PAI-1 released to the CCD18-Co colon fibroblasts culture media
783 after 48 h of treatment as measured by ELISA assays after exposure to IL-1 β (1 ng/mL)
784 or TNF- α (50 ng/mL), alone or in combination with Uro-A (40 μ M) or the MIX
785 metabolites (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA). Data are presented as the
786 mean value from three independent experiments \pm SD. Symbols indicate differences
787 from cytokine-treated samples, # $P < 0.1$, * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

788

789 **Figure 5.** Effects of Uro-A (40 μ M), Uro-B (5 μ M), EA (1 μ M) and a mixture of these
790 molecules (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA; MIX) on adhesiveness of
791 CCD18-Co to THP-1 monocytes: a) co-treatment with IL-1 β (1 ng/mL), b) co-treatment
792 with TNF- α (50 ng/mL), and c) in the absence of the inflammatory cytokines. Colon
793 fibroblasts were exposed to the different treatments for 12 h and adhesion to monocytes
794 measured. The results from three separate experiments are expressed as meanpercentage
795 of untreated control \pm SD. Symbols indicate differences from cytokine treated samples,
796 * $P < 0.05$, *** $P < 0.001$.

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798 **Figure 6.** Levels of selected cytokines and adhesion molecules as measured by ELISA
799 assays in the supernatants or cell extracts from CCD18-Co colon fibroblasts exposed to
800 IL-1 β (1 ng/mL) or TNF- α (50 ng/mL), alone or in combination with Uro-A (40 μ M) or
801 the MIX metabolites (40 μ M Uro-A, 5 μ M Uro-B, and 1 μ M EA). a) and b) levels of
802 IL8 and CCL2 released to the cell culture media after 12 h of treatment; c) and d)
803 expression levels of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 in cell extracts after 12 h of treatment. Cell
804 extracts from two plates were pooled per experiment. Data are presented as the mean

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806 value from three independent experiments \pm SD. Symbols indicate differences from

806 cytokine-treated samples, # $P < 0.1$, * $P < 0.05$, *** $P < 0.001$.

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Table 1. Selected human growth factors involved in cell migration and wound healing with altered levels of expression in human colon fibroblasts CCD18Co as determined by RayBio antibody arrays: IL-1 β treated cells (IL-1 β , 1ng/mL) vs. control cells (CT); IL-1 β +MIX treated cells (IL-1 β +MIX) vs. IL-1 β treated cells; IL-1 β +Uro-A treated cells (IL-1 β +Uro-A) vs. IL-1 β treated cells; TNF- α treated cells (TNF- α , 50 ng/mL) vs. control cells (CT); TNF- α +MIX treated cells (TNF- α +MIX) vs. TNF- α treated cells and TNF- α +Uro-A treated cells (TNF- α +Uro-A) vs. TNF- α treated cells. Cut-off value: up-regulation fold-change ≥ 1.3 , down-regulation fold-change < -1.3 .

Protein name	Symbol	IL-1 β /CT (<i>P</i> -value)	IL-1 β +MIX / IL-1 β (<i>P</i> -value)	IL-1 β +Uro-A / IL-1 β (<i>P</i> -value)	TNF- α /CT (<i>P</i> -value)	TNF- α +MIX / TNF- α (<i>P</i> -value)	TNF- α +Uro-A / TNF- α (<i>P</i> -value)
<i>Epidermal growth factor (EGF) family</i>							
Epidermal growth factor	EGF	1.53 ^a (0.038)	-1.66	N.C.	1.66 (0.041)	-1.51 (0.029)	-1.42
Epidermal growth factor receptor	EGFR	1.80	N.C.	N.C.	1.99 (0.093)	-2.10 (0.026)	N.C.
<i>Fibroblast growth factor (FGF) family</i>							
Basic fibroblast growth factor	bFGF			-2.27			1.81
Fibroblast growth factor 4	FGF4			N.C.			-1.47
Fibroblast growth factor 6	FGF6	2.78 1.49	-2.68 -1.43		1.32 1.62	-1.51 -1.53 (0.001)	N.C.
Fibroblast growth factor 7	FGF7	2.13 (0.021)	-2.56 (0.049)	-2.28 (0.054) -2.01	1.57	5.68 (0.007)	N.C.
		2.94 (0.014)	-2.21		1.48	-1.96 (0.008)	
<i>Transforming growth factor-β (TGFβ) family</i>							
Transforming growth factor beta-1	TGF β 1	6.22 (0.093)	-1.47		N.C.	1.48	-7.19 (0.044)
Transforming growth factor beta-2	TGF β 2	1.80 (0.016)	N.C.	-2.05 (0.073) -1.59	N.C.	1.47	-1.53
Transforming growth factor beta-3	TGF β 3	2.12 (0.001)	N.C.	(0.001) -1.69 (0.001) -1.37 (0.067)	N.C.	1.67	-2.45
<i>Platelet derived growth factor (PDGF) family</i>							
Platelet-derived growth factor A chain	PDGF-AA	1.96 (0.044)	-1.46 (0.052)		N.C.	N.C.	-1.55 (0.068)

Platelet-derived growth factor subunit B (homodimer)	PDGF-BB	2.05 (0.028)	-1.77 (0.088)	-1.64	1.41	-1.84	-1.55
Platelet-derived growth factor subunit B (heterodimer)	PDGF-AB	1.88 (0.032)	-1.51	-1.53 (0.074)	1.33	-1.45	-1.86 (0.047)
Platelet-derived growth factor receptor, alpha polypeptide	PDGF-R- α	2.75 (0.001)	-1.49 (0.042)	-1.76 (0.010)	1.53	-1.41	-2.29 (0.007)
Beta-type platelet-derived growth factor receptor	PDGF-R- β	1.78 (0.091)	-1.56	N.C.	1.51	-1.36	-2.21 (0.061)
<i>Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) family</i>							
Vascular endothelial growth factor A	VEGF	2.66 (0.001)	N.C.	-1.69 (0.001)	N.C.	1.43	N.C.
Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2	VEGF R2	2.40 (0.028)	N.C.	-1.75 (0.065)	N.C.	1.41	-1.47
Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 3	VEGF R3	2.25 (0.007)	N.C.	-2.04 (0.003)	N.C.	N.C.	N.C.
Vascular endothelial growth factor D	VEGF-D	2.53 (0.001)	-1.39 (0.040)	-1.99 (0.001)	N.C.	N.C.	-1.81
Placental growth factor	PlGF	2.42 (0.006)	-1.61 (0.082)	-1.66 (0.031)	1.84 (0.095)	-2.18 (0.068)	-2.24 (0.025)
<i>Macrophage colony-stimulating factor family</i>							
Macrophage colony-stimulating factor 1	M-CSF	1.77 (0.028)	-1.60 (0.007)	-1.46 (0.026)	1.52	5.08	-2.66 (0.016)
Macrophage colony stimulating factor receptor	M-CSFR	1.68 (0.007)	N.C.	-1.53 (0.041)	N.C.	N.C.	-1.73 (0.072)
Granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor	GM-CSF	8.05 (0.029)	-1.80	-2.22 (0.093)	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
<i>IGF family</i>							
Insulin-like growth factor I	IGF-I	1.92 (0.021)	-1.51	-1.41	1.62 (0.066)	-2.13 (0.006)	-1.37
Insulin-like growth factor-binding protein 2	IGFBP-2	1.45 (0.082)	-1.32	-1.43 (0.074)	1.40	-1.35	N.C.
Insulin-like growth factor binding protein-3	IGFBP-3	2.45 (0.037)	-1.43	N.C.	1.71	-1.94 (0.005)	1.40
Insulin-like growth factor 1 soluble receptor	IGF-I SR	1.71	-1.51 (0.057)	-1.38	1.76 (0.073)	-2.35 (0.003)	N.C.

^a: Data (fold-change after 48 h of exposure) are the mean value from three (IL-1 β treated cells) or two (TNF- α treated cells) independent experiments. Cell extracts from two plates were pooled and hybridized onto one antibody array per experiment. Proteins are represented in duplicate on the chip. Estimated *P* values < 0.1 are indicated. N.C.: not changed. N.D.: not detected. Shaded cells indicate comparable results (same change direction) between IL-1 β - and TNF- α -stimulated cells.

Table 2. Selected adhesion proteins with altered levels of expression in human colon fibroblasts CCD18Co as determined by RayBio antibody arrays: TNF- α treated cells (TNF- α , 50 ng/mL) vs. control cells (CT) and TNF- α +MIX treated cells (TNF- α +MIX) vs. TNF- α treated cells. Cut-off value: up-regulation fold-change ≥ 1.3 , down-regulation fold-change < -1.3 .

Protein name	Symbol	TNF- α /CT ^a (<i>P</i> -value)	TNF- α +MIX /TNF- α (<i>P</i> -value)
Interleukin 8	IL-8	7.02 (0.017)	-1.75
Chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 2	CCL2	2.98 (0.037)	-1.41 (0.003)
Intercellular adhesion molecule 1	ICAM-1	1.53	N.C.
Vascular cell adhesion molecule 1	VCAM-1	3.92 (0.001)	N.C.
Activated leukocyte cell adhesion molecule	ALCAM	1.72	-1.61
Basal cell adhesion molecule (Lutheran blood group)	BCAM	1.44	-1.69
Cadherin 1, type 1, E-cadherin (epithelial)	CDH1	1.85 (0.015)	-2.70 (0.044)

^a: Data (fold-change after 12 h of exposure) are the mean value from two independent experiments. Cell extracts from two plates were pooled and hybridized onto one antibody array per experiment. Proteins are represented in duplicate on the chip. Estimated *P* values < 0.1 are indicated. N.C.: not changed.

Figure 1

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5

Figure 6.

